

PSYCHOLOGICAL VIEWS OF ADOLESCENT PATIENTS WITH VITILIGO DISEASE

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Annotation: this article provides a brief overview of the epidemiology and social significance of vitiligo in adolescents, the main symptoms of the disease, pathogenesis, clinical signs of the disease, and treatments.

Keywords: adolescent vitiligo patients, choreoretinitis, leukoderma, dysbacteriosis, malabsorption syndrome.

The initial stage, which is characterized by the formation of a single point on the skin. Depending on the nature of the disease, this stage then progresses to a progressive, stable or repigmentation stage.

The stationary stage, there is one stain on the patient's skin, which is characterized by being in a stable state. This stain does not enlarge for a long time, new spots do not appear.

Repigmentation stage. Most often, this stage is observed during the spontaneous formation of a stain caused by therapeutic measures, for example, taking certain drugs. Alas, independent and complete repigmentation in this form of skin disease is considered a very rare condition.

But it is important to know that spots are formed not in a mandatory way, but only under the influence of risk factors. For this reason, the child of a parent with vitiligo can live a lifetime without experiencing the symptoms. At the same time, children with severe family Anamnesis are part of the risk group.

Scientists have studied some of the most common haplotypes of patients with vitiligo. But the number of their occurrence is constantly changing and depends on the population under study. Therefore, more attention should be paid to the factors that motivate depigmentation.

Naturally, mothers who are exposed to vitiligo are at risk from the transmission of skin pathology to their child. In this case, it is important not to confuse one thing: a child born will not have the disease itself (that is, there will be no congenital spots on it), but a predisposition to its development. Therefore, if a mother or other family member has vitiligo, their children should be exposed as little as possible to the effects of motivating factors. Among them are psychological and physical injuries, ultraviolet rays, burns, etc.

If the disease affects a woman during pregnancy, it does not affect the development of her fetus and does not pose a risk. But hormonal changes occur during pregnancy, which can lead to a faster spread of the disease.

In newborns, symptoms of vitiligo are rarely detected. For this reason, if white spots are detected on the baby's skin, then psoriasis, white or colored ferruginous, as well as allergies can be suspected. But unlike vitiligo, in this case, skin tightness is also noted.

The answer to this question is obvious — No, it is not transmitted. This disease is not an infection, and the person exposed to it does not pose a threat to others in terms of transmission of the disease. Therefore, it is possible to communicate without fear with people with such spots on their skin.

If one or more white spots have appeared on the skin, then it is necessary to look at the dermatologist-doctor. It examines the skin with a special lamp and determines the nature of

depigmentation. If necessary, material is taken to clarify the diagnosis. These methods are important because vitiligo should be distinguished from other skin diseases.

When it comes to therapy, despite the fact that there are cases of complete and spontaneous healing from vitiligo, the disease is more likely to develop more strongly without appropriate treatment. It is important to be able to choose the right medications, considering that pathology is often accompanied by other diseases.

References:

1. Sharipova G. I. The use of flavonoid based medications in the treatment of inflammatory diseases in oral mucus //Asian journal of Pharmaceutical and biological research. India. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 1. – C. 2231-2218. (Impact factor: 4.465)
2. Sharipova G. I.Changes in the content of trace elements in the saliva of patients in the treatment of patients with traumatic stomatitis with flavonoid-based drugs // Journal of research in health science. Iran. – 2022. – T. 6. – № 1-2. – C. 23-26. (Scopus)
3. Sharipova G. I., Nuraliyev N. A. General description and research methods used in children with traumatic stomatitis // European Journal of Research. Austria. – 2022.– T. 7. – № 1. – C. 51-56. (Impact factor: 4.981)
4. Sharipova G. I. Paediatric Lazer Dentistry //International Journal of Culture and Modernity. Spain. – 2022. – T. 12. – C. 33-37.
5. Sharipova G. I. The effectiveness of the use of magnetic-infrared-laser therapy in traumatic injuries of oral tissues in preschool children //Journal of Academic Leadership. India. – 2022. – T. 21. – №. 1.
6. Sharipova G. I. Discussion of results of personal studies in the use of mil therapy in the treatment of trauma to the oral mucosa //European journal of molecular medicine. Germany. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 17-21.
7. Sharipova G. I. Peculiarities of the morphological structure of the oral mucosa in young children // International journal of conference series on education and social sciences. (Online) May. Turkey. – 2022. – C. 36-37.
8. Sharipova G. I. Dynamics of cytological changes in the state of periodontal tissue under the influence of dental treatment prophylactic complex in young children with traumatic stomatitis // Multidiscipline Proceedings of digital fashion conference April. Korea. – 2022. – C. 103-105.
9. Sharipova G.I. Assessment of comprehensive dental treatment and prevention of dental diseases in children with traumatic stomatitis // National research in Uzbekistan: periodical conferences: Part 18. Tashkent. -2021. - S. 14-15.
10. Sharipova G.I. Effectiveness of applying magnetic-infrared-laser therapy in the complex treatment of soft tissue injuries of the oral cavity in preschool children // Methodological recommendation. Bukhara. - 2022. - 21 p
11. Karshiyeva D.R.,The Importance of Water Quality and Quantity in Strengthening the Health and Living Conditions of the Population//CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES. Voleme: 02 Issue: 05I Oct 28 2021 Page 399-402
12. Karshiyeva D.R.,The Role Of Human Healthy And Safe Lifestyle In The Period
13. Of Global Pandemic-Covid 19//The American Journal of Applied Sciences.Voleme: 02 Issue: 11-15I November 28, 2020 ISSN: 2689-0992. Page 78-81

14. Karshieva Dilovar Rustamovna. THE EFFECT OF TOBACCO SMOKING ON THE ORGANS AND TISSUES OF THE ORAL CAVITY / / World Bulletin of Public Health (WBPH) Volume-19, February 2023 ISSN: 2749-3644

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